

Spectrophotometric Determination of Cerium(IV) in Aqueous Medium with 4-Sulpho-2-aminobenzenethiol and Its Studies

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A simple, sensitive and selective spectrophotometric method of determination of cerium(IV) complex with a new thiol reagent has been reported here. The blue-violet complex is formed at 0.4-2.88 M hydrochloric acid absorbs maximum at 560 nm, and it is stable for 3 h. Beer's law is obeyed from 0.4 to 18 ppm of Ce^{IV} . The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity values are $8.06 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0172 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2} Ce^{IV}$, respectively at 560 nm. A fifty-fold excess of Zr^{IV} , Th^{IV} , Ti^{IV} , Mo^{VI} , W^{VI} , U^{VI} , Mn^{II} , Zn^{II} , Pb^{II} , Cr^{III} , Cd^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Cu^{II} , and seventeen anions do not interfere in the determination. The cerium(IV)-thiol composition determined by photometric method is found to be 1 : 2.

It is well known that cerium(III) forms chelate complexes with a number of ligands. But, cerium(IV) forms complexes with chelating reagents and its kinetically controlled reduction to Ce^{III} by reducing reagents give much importance in analytical chemistry. Usually, Ce^{IV} do not form stable coloured chelate complexes due to facile reduction of atomic groupings and also by the heat of the reaction. Oxidised coloured products are obtained. Oxidative products which have been utilised very often in the determination of the metal are also very numerous¹⁻³.

Traces of Ce^{IV} is determined by titrimetric, kinetic, spectrophotometric^{4-7,14} and fluorimetric methods⁸⁻¹³.

In this paper, a spectrophotometric method of determination of cerium(IV) with the thiol reagent has been developed in aqueous solution based on the complex formation in hydrochloric acid medium. The blue-violet complex is formed at 1.8 M HCl and 2 M H_2SO_4 media. Cerium(III) forms no complex under any condition with 4-sulpho-2-aminobenzenethiol. Previously, the reagent was used for direct gravimetric determination of mercury(II) as yellow complex, and spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) as mixed ligand complex with oxalic acid¹⁵. Cerium(IV) in trace concentration (1 ppm) can easily be determined by the present method.

Experimental

A Hilger-Uvispek spectrophotometer was used for absorption measurements.

4-Sulpho-2-aminobenzenethiol was prepared as reported earlier¹⁵. A 1% aqueous solution was freshly prepared before use in double-distilled water. A stock solution of cerium(IV) ammonium

sulphate (E. Merck) was prepared in double-distilled water and standardised¹⁶. More dilute solutions ($10^{-5}M$) were obtained by diluting it with double-distilled water. The solutions of diverse ions were prepared from their A.R. grade salts and standardised conventionally. The rare earth metal solutions were obtained by standard procedures. S-Benzylthiuronium chloride (E. Merck) was directly used for extraction studies and isolation of the cerium(IV) complex. All other chemicals and solvents used were of G.R. grade.

Procedure : To an aliquot of cerium(IV) solution (100 μg) was added aqueous solution of the reagent in excess (7 ml, 1%), and the acidity was adjusted to 1.9 M HCl in a 25 ml standard flask. After 45 min the volume was made up with double-distilled water at room temperature. A reagent blank was prepared similarly. The absorbance of the blue-violet cerium(IV) complex was measured against water blank at 560 nm (reagent blank does not absorb). The unknown cerium content could be determined from the calibration curve constructed.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance curve : The reagent blank showed no absorption in the range 400-800 nm. The absorbance of the blue-violet cerium(IV) complex was measured from 400 to 800 nm and the spectra showed double peaks one at 450 nm and maximum at 560 nm (Fig. 1).

Optimum reaction conditions : The absorbance of a series of solutions at varying acidity of HCl and reagent were measured for 8 ppm Ce^{IV} complex at 560 nm against water blank. The Ce^{IV} complex is formed between 0.1 and 5.8 M HCl acid

and the optimum range of acidity is 0.4-2.88 M. A lower molar absorptivity was obtained with 1-3 ml concentrated HCl. Acidity was always adjusted to 1.92 M by adding 4 ml concentrated HCl.

Fig. 1. Absorbance spectra of cerium(IV) complex, 8 ppm.

A 0.1-1.10 ml of 1% aqueous solution of reagent formed the cerium(IV) complexes with 4 ml of concentrated HCl. 5.5 ml of 1% solution was sufficient for full colour development and the optimum range is 5.5-9 ml of 1% reagent. For complex formation 7 ml of 1% reagent was always used. The spectra indicated maxima at 550-570 nm measured against water blank.

The order of addition of the reagents have indicated that the acid should always be added after reagent. The colour developed at room temperature slowly on standing for 45 min. The mixture on heating over water-bath gives a yellow complex; the blue-violet complex fully formed within 35-60 min after addition. The cerium(IV) complex was stable for 3 h at room temperature.

Beer's law, optimum range, photometric error, molar absorptivity and sensitivity: The cerium(IV) complex obeys Beer's law from 0.5 to 18 ppm of Ce^{IV} at 560 nm (Fig. 2). The optimum range of determination obtained from Ringbom's curve is 1.5-15 ppm of the metal¹⁷. The percent relative photometric error per 1% absolute photometric error calculated by Ayre's equation¹⁸ is 2.7. The molar absorptivity calculated from Beer's law for the complex and Sandell's sensitivity of the reaction¹⁹ are $8.06 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0173 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2} Ce^{IV}$ at 560 nm, respectively.

Composition of complex: The composition of the complex was determined by the method of continuous variation and mole-ratio method^{20,21}. Equimolar solutions ($7.139 \times 10^{-4} M$) of cerium(IV)

Fig. 2. Beer's law plot.

and the reagent were mixed in a complementary mixture of 12 ml volume following the procedure. The plot of absorbance against $M/(M+R)$ ratio showed a 1 : 2 (Ce^{IV} : thiol) composition at 560 nm. The composition was verified by mole-ratio method using the equimolar solutions and a constant metal concentration. The plot of absorbance against the mole-fraction of the metal showed a break at a 1 : 2, metal to reagent ratio in the complex at 560 nm.

Effect of diverse ions: Studies on the effect of diverse ions were made using 8 ppm cerium(IV) and the absorbances were measured at 560 nm. Fifty-fold excess of Pb^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Mn^{II} , Cr^{III} , Mn^{VII} , Cr^{VI} , Al^{III} , Ti^{IV} , Mo^{VI} , W^{VI} , U^{VI} do not interfere. Permanganate and dichromate interferences were removed using 1 ml acetone in the general procedure. Twentyfive-fold excess of Bi^{III} , Sn^{II} , Zr^{IV} and Th^{IV} do not interfere. The tolerance limit for Cu^{II} is low and amounts to five-fold excess, but no interference is observed in presence of thiourea. Twentyfive-fold excess of citrate, oxalate, EDTA, and fifty-fold excess of tartrate showed no interference. Acetate, fluoride, phosphate, perchlorate, thiosulphate, borate, persulphate, bromate, iodate, chloride, sulphate, nitrate, acetate and thiourea do not interfere. Fe^{III} , Hg^{II} , Cr^{VI} , thiocyanate and cyanide indicate strong interference. Fe^{II} strongly interferes in absence of any masking agent.

Solvent extraction of cerium(IV): Separation of cerium(IV) from other metal ions by solvent extraction is not normally accomplished with the thiol reagent. The complex has been extracted with benzylisothiurea hydrochloride as the extractant in isoamyl alcohol and chloroform, but it is not very stable. The complex is soluble in ethanol,

acetone and water giving a light violet colour which turned deep violet in presence of mineral acids (HCl, HNO₃). In presence of nitric acid the violet extract is stable, but a slight bluish precipitate has been observed. The complex is not extracted with the salt in presence of H₂SO₄. The above experiments show that a cerium(IV) complex is always formed in solution and the metal can be separated using the S-benzylthiuronium chloride [C₆H₅.CH₂.S.C(NH).NH₂]₂Cl from hydrochloric and nitric acid media. Cerium as one of the composite rare earth metal in monozite mineral can be separated by this method.

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